

A Stereoselective Synthesis of *N*-[7-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-2*E*,6*E*-heptadienyl]pyrrolidine (Sarmentosine). A New Alkamide isolated from *Pipersarmentosum*

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A convenient stereoselective synthesis of *N*-[7-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2*E*,6*E*-heptadienyl]pyrrolidine (1), an alkaloid isolated from the genus *piper*, has been performed starting from piperonal, where the stereochemistry was fixed by utilising the modified Wittig reaction.

Recently an unsaturated amide, sarmentosine, established as *N*-[7-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-2*E*,6*E*-heptadienyl]pyrrolidine (1) on the basis of its spectral properties, has been isolated from the fruits of piper¹. Compounds similar to 1 are responsible for pungent taste of black piper^{2,3} and show antitumor activity⁴. We report here a synthesis of 1, the salient feature being the specific fixation of double bond with proper stereochemistry through Emmons-Horner modified Wittig reaction (Scheme 1).

Piperonal (2) was subjected to modified Wittig reaction⁵ using dimethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl ethylphosphonate in 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME) and NaH as a base to afford conjugated ester (3). Reduction of 3 with modified LAH reagent, presumably lithium aluminium monoethoxyhydride prepared *in situ* from LAH and absolute ethanol⁶ in ether furnished the allylic alcohol (4). 4 was converted into its mesylate 5⁷ which was reacted further with ethyl monosodiummalonate in benzene-DMF⁸ to furnish the diester (6). 6 when heated with a mixture of moist NaCl and DMSO⁹ at 160–65° yielded the monoester (7). Reduction

of 7 with LAH modified with absolute ethanol in ether followed by pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) oxidation¹⁰ in dry CH₂Cl₂, led to the aldehyde (9). Condensation of 9 with the anion of dimethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl ethylphosphonate in dry DME produced the unsaturated ester (10) which on hydrolysis with alcoholic KOH produced the conjugated acid (11). Condensation of 11 with pyrrolidine using POCl₃ and triethylamine as base in dry CH₂Cl₂ gave sarmentosine (1) which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate as eluent. Its spectral data were found to be in agreement with the structure (1)¹. Further confirmation of the structure was deduced from ¹³C nmr spectrum which was found to be identical with the reported one¹.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded using thin film on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 337 spectrophotometer with NaCl optics, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra on Varian EM 390 and Jeol FX 90 Q FT NMR spectrometers using TMS as an internal standard, uv spectra on a Hitachi 330 UV spectrophotometer, and mass spectra on a VG micromass 7070 M spectrometer. Neutral alumina of Brockman activity (B.D.H.) and silica gel (100–200 mesh Acme) were used for column chromatography. All solvents and reagents were purified and dried by standard procedures. Unless otherwise stated, all the organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

Ethyl 3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)propan-2-(E)-enoate (3): A 50% mineral suspension of NaH (50%; 5.28 g, 110 mmol) washed with *n*-hexane was placed in 1,2-dimethoxyethane (110 ml) and dimethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-methylphosphonate (23.5 g, 120 mmol) was added dropwise below 20° with continuous stirring until the gas evolution ceased. To the resulting yellow solution was added the aldehyde (2; 15.0 g, 100 mmol) slowly below 10°. Stirring was then continued for 4 h. Thereafter the reaction mixture was heated at 60° for 1 h, decomposed with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ether-layer was separated and successively washed with water and brine and dried. Solvent removal and column chromatography

Scheme 1. Reagents : (a) NaH, (CH₃O)₂P(O)CH₂COOEt, (b) LAH, EtOH, (c) MeSO₂Cl, NEt₃, (d) NaCH(COOEt)₂, benzene, (e) DMSO-H₂O, 160°. (f) LAH, EtOH, (g) PCC, (h) NaH, (MeO)₂P(O)CH₂COOEt, (i) KOH, MeOH, (j) POCl₃, NEt₃, pyrrolidine.

of the residue on silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate afforded **3** (15.5 g, 70%), (Found C, 65.00, H, 5.84 $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.15, H, 5.92%), $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 2900, 1720, 1630, 1600, 1500, 1450, 1380, 1240, 1120, 1035, 860, 830 and 805 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.35 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, CH_3), 4.40 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, CH_2), 6.00 (2H, s, $-O-CH_2-O-$), 6.10 (1H, d, J 15.5 Hz, $CH=CH-COOC_2H_5$), 6.25 (1H, J 15.5 Hz, $CH=CH-COOC_2H_5$), 6.60–6.90 (3H, m, ArH).

3-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)prop (E)-enol (4) To a stirred slurry of LAH (1.9 g, 50 mmol) in anhydrous ether (100 ml) was added absolute ethanol (0.15 g, 3.25 mmol) dropwise and the reaction allowed to subside. The reagent thus obtained was added to a stirred solution of the ester (**3**, 9.94 g, 45 mmol) in ether (150 ml) at 0–5° in small portions during 30 min. The reaction mixture was decomposed carefully by adding water, filtered, the filtrate washed with water and brine and dried. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish **4** (6.56 g, 82%), (Found C, 67.30, H, 5.60 $C_{10}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 67.41, H, 5.66%), $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 3340, 2900, 1420, 1350, 1300, 1235, 1050, 1020 and 815 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 3.5 (1H, br s, OH exchangeable with D_2O), 4.25 (2H, d, CH_2-O), 5.95 (1H, m, olefinic proton), 6.05 (2H, s, $-O-CH_2-O-$), 6.20 (1H, d, olefinic proton), 6.7–7.0 (3H, m, ArH).

3-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)prop 2(E) methane sulphonate (5) To a stirred solution of alcohol **4** (6.50 g, 36.5 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (50 ml) containing 50% molar excess of NEt_3 , maintained at 0 to –10°, was added methanesulphonyl chloride (5.50 g, 47.8 mmol) in methylene chloride (20 ml). Stirring of the mixture was continued for 30 min more. The reaction mixture was then washed successively with dilute HCl (10%), saturated aqueous $NaHCO_3$, water and brine and dried ($CaCl_2$). Solvent evaporation gave **5** (8.04 g, 86%) which was used as such in the next operation.

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-5-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-4-pentenoate (6) The mesylate (**5**, 8.00 g, 31.30 mmol) was added to ethyl monosodiummalonate (from sodium 36.9 g-atom and ethyl malonate 31.8 mmol) in dry benzene (100 ml) in presence of DMF (10 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 16 h, then treated with water and the aqueous layer was back-extracted with ether (50 ml). The combined organic extracts were washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatographic separation using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate as eluent afforded **6** (5.64 g, 59%), (Found C, 62.61, H, 5.80 $C_{16}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 62.74, H, 5.92%), $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 2910, 1730, 1750, 1430, 1350, 1085, 1040, 855, 820, 790 and 715 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.20 (6H, m, $2 \times CH_3$), 2.55 (2H, m, CH_2), 3.23 (1H, t, CH), 4.17 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2$), 5.85 (1H, m, olefinic proton), 6.05 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.20 (1H, d,

olefinic proton), 6.80–7.05 (3H, m, ArH).

Ethyl 5-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl) pent 4 enoate (7) The diester (**6**, 5.60 g, 18.35 mmol) was heated for 3 h at 160–65° in DMSO (40 ml) containing a few drops of water (33.3 mmol) and NaCl (10.76 g, 18.4 mmol). DMSO was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated with cold water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water several times and finally washed with brine and dried. Solvent removal and column chromatography on silica gel eluting with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate yielded **7** (3.82 g, 84%), (Found C, 67.58, H, 6.39 $C_{14}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 67.73, H, 6.49%), $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 2900, 1735, 1610, 1345, 1330, 1150, 1120, 1090, 1035, 830, 815, 785 and 735 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.22 (3H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH_3), 2.50 (4H, m, allylic protons), 4.13 (2H, g, J 6.0 Hz, CH_2), 5.87 (1H, m, olefinic proton), 5.96 (2H, s, $-O-CH_2-O-$), 6.20 (1H, d, olefinic proton), 6.75–6.95 (3H, m, ArH).

Ethyl 5-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl) pent 4 eno (8) It was prepared according to the procedure described for **4**.

5-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)pent-1 enal (9) To a suspension of pyridinium chlorochromate (2.20 g, 10.18 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (30 ml) was added the alcohol (**8**, 1.37 g, 6.67 mmol) in methylene chloride (20 ml) in one lot with stirring at 10°. Stirring was continued for 4 h, then ether (50 ml) was added to it and the supernatant liquid decanted from the black gum. The insoluble residue was washed with anhydrous ether (3–50 ml) when a black granular solid was obtained. The combined organic extracts were passed through a short column of neutral alumina and dried. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave the sharp smelling aldehyde (1.0 g, 78%), (Found C, 67.87, H, 7.13 $C_{11}H_{14}O$ requires C, 68.06, H, 7.26%), $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 2710, 1710, 1600, 1240, 1190, 1040, 1005, 925 and 800 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.48 (4H, m, allylic protons), 5.92 (1H, m, olefinic proton), 6.00 (2H, s, $-O-CH_2-O-$), 6.24 (1H, d, olefinic proton), 6.80–6.98 (3H, m, ArH), 9.82 (1H, br s, CHO).

Ethyl 7-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)hepta 2(E) 6(E) dienoate (10) It was prepared according to the procedure as described for **3**. (Found C, 69.89, H, 6.52 $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.06, H, 6.61%), $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 1730, 1600, 1260, 1195, 1100, 1050, 930, 820 and 710 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.23 (3H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH_3), 2.45 (4H, m, allylic protons), 4.12 (2H, g, J 6.0 Hz, CH_2), 5.82–7.05 (9H, m, ArH, $-O-CH_2-O-$, 4 olefinic protons).

7-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)hepta 2(E) 6(E) dienol acid (11) A methanolic solution (40 ml) of the ester (**10**, 1.39 g, 5.10 mmol) was added to a saturated solution of KOH (0.30 g, 5.36 mmol) in methanol and the contents were stirred for 10 h at room temperature. The methanol was then evaporated, the residue treated with water (20 ml) and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer

was acidified with dilute HCl (10%) and extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml). The combined ether extracts was washed with water and brine and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatographic purification yielded **11** (0.88 g, 70%), (Found : C, 68.11; H, 5.61, C₁₄H₁₄O₄ requires : C, 68.28; H, 5.73%); $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 3400–2500 br, 1710, 1600, 1260, 1190, 1050, 930, 820 and 710 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.60 (4H, m, allylic protons), 5.75–5.90 (2H, m, olefinic H), 6.02 (2H, s, -O-CH₂-O-), 6.25–6.40 (2H, m, olefinic protons), 6.80–7.00 (3H, m, ArH), 10.50 (1H, br s, COOH, exchangeable with D₂O).

N-[7-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-2(E), 6(E)-heptadienyl]pyrrolidine (*Sarmentosine*) (**1**): POCl₃ (phosphorus oxychloride) (0.58 g, 3.8 mmol) in methylene chloride (20 ml) was added dropwise to a well-stirred solution of **11** (0.86 g, 3.5 mmol), triethylamine (0.73 ml, 5.25 mmol) and pyrrolidine (0.25 g, 3.5 mmol) at 0° in methylene chloride (50 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 0° and another 1 h at room temperature. The contents were then poured in cold water and extracted with methylene chloride (3 × 20 ml). The organic layer was washed with saturated NaHCO₃ solution (15%), water and brine and dried. Evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure followed by chromatographic purification of the residue over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (8 : 2) afforded **1** (0.89 g, 86%; single spot tlc), m.p. 77.5–79.5°, (Found : C, 72.10; H, 7.00; N, 4.20, C₁₈H₂₁O₃N requires :

C, 72.60; H, 7.00; N, 4.30%); m/z 299 (M^+); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 216 (36700), 268 (18700), 309 nm (8900); $\nu_{\max}$ (CCl₄) 2860, 1650, 1615, 1435, 1245, 1040 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.91 (4H, m, β , β'), 2.3–2.55 (4H, br s, allylic methylenes), 3.50 (4H, m, α , α'), 5.92 (2H, s, 7', -O-CH₂-O-), 6.00 (1H, d t, J 15.0, 6.2 Hz, 6-H), 6.15 (1H, d, J 15.0 Hz, 2-H), 6.29 (1H, d, J 15.0 Hz, 7-H), 6.85–6.90 (4H, m, 2'-H, 5'-H, 6'-H, 3-H); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃) 24.19 (t), 26.12 (t), 31.50 (t), 32.20 (t), 45.61 (t), 46.41 (t), 100.89 (t), 105.10 (d), 108.52 (d), 120.28 (d), 122.22 (d), 127.40 (d), 130.18 (d), 132.20 (s), 144.36 (d), 146.66 (s), 147.85 (s), 164.63 (s).

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